

left overnight at 0°. Usual work-up gave a product which was repeatedly crystallised after charcoalisation from MeOH to yield **1b**, m.p. 228° (Found: M^+ 542. $C_{30}H_{46}O_8$ requires: 542); ν_{\max} (nujol) 3560 (free OH), 1733 and 1245 cm^{-1} (acetoxy groups); m/z 542 (15%, M^+), 524 (20, $M-H_2O$), 482 (25, $M-CH_3COOH$), 424 (40, $M-CH_3COOH-CH_3COCH_3$), 422 (10, $M-2CH_3COOH$), 404 (25, $M-2CH_3COOH-H_2O$), 364 (30, m/z 424- CH_3COOH), 265 (7, **b**), 247 (7, **d**), 187 (78, **b**- H_2O-CH_3COOH or **d**- CH_3COOH) and 59

+OH

(31, CH_3CCH_3); δ (90 MHz, $CDCl_3$) 5.55 (1H, t, J 4Hz, 6-H), 4.89 (1H, br m, $W_{1/2}$ 24Hz, 16 α -H), 4.49 (1H, m, $W_{1/2}$ 16Hz, 3 α -H), 3.50 (1H, s, disappeared on D_2O exchange, OH), 2.02, 2.01 (3H each, s, $2 \times OCOCH_3$), 1.20, 1.20, 1.20, 1.17, 1.12, 1.07, 1.03, 0.73 (3H each, s, $8 \times tert-CH_3$). For ^{13}C nmr data vide Ref. 3.

Oxidation of mollugogenol-G with CrO_3/Py complex: Ice-cold mollugogenol-G (100 mg) in pyridine (2.5 ml) was treated with a slurry of CrO_3 -pyridine complex (prepared from 300 mg CrO_3 and 5 ml pyridine) at 0° with stirring and left overnight. Usual work-up afforded a mass showing two spots in tlc. Cc and repeated crystallisations from MeOH furnished **1c**, m.p. 232-35° (Found: C, 78.98; H, 10.43. $C_{30}H_{46}O_8$ requires: C, 79.25; H, 10.20%); M^+ 454; and **1d**, m.p. 226-27° (Found: C, 78.61; H, 10.82. $C_{30}H_{46}O_8$ requires: C, 78.90; H, 10.59%); M^+ 456.

Treatment of 1a with ethanolic HCl: Compound **1a** (5 mg) in dry EtOH (1 ml) was treated with dry ethanolic HCl (10%, 1 ml) and refluxed on a steam-bath for 3 h. Crushed ice was poured into the reaction mixture and the precipitate was filtered and washed with water. The product (diene) showed triple absorption maxima at 243, 251 and 261 nm and a shoulder at 290 nm.

Treatment of the monohydroxydiketone (1c) with ethanolic HCl: The monohydroxydiketone (**1c**; 5 mg) in dry EtOH (1 ml) was refluxed with dry ethanolic HCl (10%; 1 ml) on a steam-bath for 3 h. Work-up as above afforded a product (α,β -unsaturated-ketone) which showed λ_{\max} (EtOH) at 255 nm.

Hydrogenation of mollugogenol-G (1a): Adam's catalyst (15 mg) suspended in glacial acetic acid was shaken in an atmosphere of hydrogen for 1 h at room temperature and pressure. Mollugogenol-G (15 mg) in glacial acetic acid (4 ml) was added to it and the mixture shaken in an atmosphere of hydrogen for 30 h at room temperature and pressure. On working up in the usual way only unreacted mollugogenol-G was recovered.

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Chemical Examination of *Cassia pumila* Lam.

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IN connection of our works on *Cassia*¹ species, the chemical investigation of *Cassia pumila* Lam. (*Leguminosae*) on which no phytochemical works seems to have been reported so far, has been undertaken. *C. pumila*² is a plant growing abundantly throughout India and is commonly used as purgative.

The air-dried powdered whole plant of *C. pumila* was extracted successively with petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) and chloroform. The concentrated petroleum ether extract was chromatographed over silica gel. Elution of the column with petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°)-benzene (1:1) mixture furnished a white crystalline solid, m.p. 88-90°, ν_{\max} (KBr) 3440 cm^{-1} (OH); δ 0.65 (3H, t, CH_3), 1.40 (64H, s, $32 \times CH_2$) and 3.50 (2H, CH_2OH); m/z 494 (M^+), 476 and 463. It was identified as tetratriacontanol by the usual comparison (m.m.p., co-tlc and co-ir) with an authentic sample.

The concentrated chloroform extract of the defatted whole plant was subjected to chromatographic separation over silica gel with solvents of increasing polarity. The benzene elute afforded a solid crystallised from light petrol (b.p. 60-80°), $C_{34}H_{66}O_8$ (M^+ 230), m.p. 123-25°; λ_{\max} (EtOH) 220, 272 and 330 nm; ν_{\max} (KBr) 1715 (coumarin lactone), 1625, 1485 (aromatic unsaturation) and 1140 cm^{-1} (C-O-C). The spectral data suggest that the compound is a coumarin derivative. The 1H nmr spectrum (90 MHz, $CDCl_3$) is also consistent with the above view and displayed signals at δ 7.45

(1H, s, C₆ coumarin proton) and 6.20 (1H, s, C₄ coumarin protons), 7.35 (1H, s, ArH), 6.75 (1H, s, ArH), 2.80, 1.80 (2H each, chroman CH₂CH₂) and 1.40 (6H, s, O-C(CH₃)₂) revealing the presence of a coumarin and chroman ring in the compound. The above spectral data were found to be very similar to those reported for dihydroxanthyletin⁴. The identity of the two compounds was established by comparison of physical constants and uv, ir and nmr spectral data.

Further elution of the column with benzene-chloroform (1:1) mixture yielded a yellow solid crystallised from glacial acetic acid as yellow leaflets, C₁₆H₁₂O₆ (M⁺ 284), m.p. 210; λ_{max} (EtOH) 260, 272, 290, 415 and 435 nm; ν_{max} (KBr) 3360 (bonded OH), 1680 (non-chelated C=O), 1625 cm⁻¹ (conjugated chelated C=O); δ 2.30 (3H, s, aromatic C-methyl), 3.90 (3H, s, aromatic methoxyl), 6.90 (2H, s, C₆-H and C₇-H), 7.00 (1H, s, C₂-OH) and 7.40 (1H, s, C₄-H). It responded to methanolic magnesium acetate test for anthraquinones⁴ and was characterised as physcion⁵ by direct comparison (m.m.p., co-tlc and co-ir) with the authentic sample.

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Phytochemical Examination of the Leaves of *Anacardium occidentale*

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LITERATURE survey showed detailed reports on the bark¹, cashew apple² and nutshell³ of *A. occidentale* for its flavonoidic constituents. However, a scanty work on its leaf constituents prompted

us to investigate the leaves thoroughly. The present paper deals with the isolation and characterisation of myricetin, agathisflavone, robustaflavone, amentoflavone, quercetin, kaempferol, apigenin and two glycosides, viz. quercetin-3-O-rhamnoside and quercetin-3-O-glucoside. The structure of the compounds were confirmed by their spectral data and by comparison with authentic samples.

Dried defatted leaves (2 kg), procured from Mannarghat, Kerla (India), were extracted exhaustively with methanol. The methanol concentrate was refluxed successively with benzene, chloroform, ethyl acetate and acetone. The chloroform, ethyl acetate and acetone concentrates were combined and treated with boiling water. The water-insoluble fraction on tlc examination (benzene-pyridine-formic acid, 36:9:5) revealed the presence of six bands which were labelled as AO-I to AO-VI, in order of increasing R_f values. They were separated by preparative tlc (B-P-F) and eluted by acetone mixed with pyridine (2%).

AO-I, m.p. 358–59°; AO-IV, m.p. 314°; AO-V, m.p. 278° and AO-VI, m.p. 346° were characterised as myricetin, quercetin, kaempferol and apigenin by comparison of nmr spectral studies of their acetates and methyl ethers with authentic samples⁴. AO-II on methylation was found to be a mixture of two compounds. The two methyl ethers were identified as hexamethyl ethers of agathisflavone⁵ and robustaflavone⁶. AO-III, m.p. 253–55°, on derivatisation gave a hexamethyl ether of amentoflavone, m.p. 226–27° and hexaacetate of amentoflavone, m.p. 240–42°⁷.

The methanol concentrate, after solvent treatment (chloroform, ethyl acetate and acetone) was found to be a mixture of two glycosides. They were separated by column chromatography over silica gel column using CCl₄-EtOAc (1:1, 1:4) mixtures as eluting solvent. The resulting two fractions were labelled as AOG-I and AOG-II.

AOG-I, m.p. 181–82°, gave green colour with ferric chloride and positive Molisch and Shinoda tests⁸. The uv spectral studies showed it to be flavonol glycoside with 3-position glycosylated. On acid hydrolysis (6% alcoholic HCl) it gave quercetin and rhamnose. The nmr spectrum of the acetate was comparable to the quercetin-3-O-rhamnoside⁴, which was further confirmed by the hydrolysis of permethylated glycoside using Hakomori method⁹. Similarly AOG-II, m.p. 235–36°, was characterised as quercetin-3-O-glucoside⁴.

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